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Mode of action and fate of microcystins in the complex soil-plant ecosystems

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25 Abstract

26 Over the last decades, global warming has increasingly stimulated the expansion of
27 cyanobacterial blooms in freshwater ecosystems worldwide, in which toxic cyanobacteria
28 produce various congeners of cyanotoxins, mainly dominated by microcystins (MCs). MCs
29 introduced into agricultural soils have deleterious effects on the germination, growth and
30 development of plants and their associated microbiota, leading to remarkable yield losses.
31 Phytotoxicity of MCs may refer to the inhibition of phosphatases activity, generating
32 deleterious reactive oxygen species, altering gene functioning and phytohormones translocation
33 within the plant. It is also known that MCs can pass through the root membrane barrier,
34 translocate within plant tissues and accumulate into different organs, including edible ones.
35 Also, MCs impact the microbial activity in soil via altering plant-bacterial symbioses and
36 decreasing bacterial growth rate of rhizospheric microbiota. Moreover, MCs can persist in
37 agricultural soils through adsorption to clay-humic acid particles and results in a long-term
38 contact with the plant-microflora complex. However, their bioavailability to plants and half-
39 life in soil seem to be influenced by biodegradation process and soil physicochemical
40 properties. This review reports the latest and most relevant information regarding MCs-
41 phytotoxicity and impact on soil microbiota, their persistence in soil, the degradation by native
42 microflora and the bioaccumulation within plant tissues.

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44 **Keywords:** Microcystins, Phytotoxicity, Plant Defense, Soil microorganisms, Soil-plant
45 transfer, Sorption

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471. Introduction

48 Over the last decades, harmful cyanobacterial blooms (HCBs) have been frequently occurring
49 worldwide in eutrophic freshwater ecosystems. Their global expansion is due to the joint effect
50 of climate warming and increased nutrient inputs due to anthropogenic activities ([Heisler et al.,](#)

51 2008; Paerl and Huisman, 2009; Paerl et al., 2011; O'Neil et al., 2012; Rigosi et al., 2014;
52 Chapra et al., 2017). Toxin producing-taxa within HCBs have been increasing in abundance
53 and producing and releasing various toxic secondary metabolites (i.e. cyanotoxins) into water
54 bodies which represent a major concern for human and ecosystem health (O'Neil et al., 2012;
55 Corbel et al., 2014a; Machado et al., 2017a). Microcystins (MCs) have been frequently reported
56 throughout the world as the most widespread cyanotoxins with more than 250 congeners (Spooft
57 and Catherine, 2017). MCs-analogues share the following cyclic heptapeptide structure: cyclo-
58 (D-Ala¹-X²-D-isoMeAsp³-Y⁴-Adda⁵-D-isoGlu⁶-Mdha⁷), where X and Y represent a variable
59 pair of L-amino acids (Puddick et al., 2014) (Fig. 1). Among others, MC-LR (L: Leucine, R:
60 Arginine) is the most toxic and prevalent MC-analogue that has been extensively studied and
61 reported (WHO, 2011). Their toxicity is attributed to the presence of Adda residue (3-amino-
62 9-methoxy-2,6,8-trimethyl-10-phenyldeca-4,6-dienoic acid) (Jaeg, 2007) (Fig. 1). MCs-
63 producing cyanobacteria belong to several genera including *Microcystis*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*,
64 *Oscillatoria*, and *Planktothrix* (Botes et al., 1982; Sivonen et al., 1990; Sivonen et al., 1992;
65 Luukkainen et al., 1993; Christiansen et al., 2003).

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75 Fig. 1. Common structure of a MC analogue: MC-LR, where Masp is methylaspartic acid, Adda
76 is 3-amino-9-methoxy-2,6,8-trimethyl-10-phenyldeca-4,6-dienoic acid and Mdha is N-
77 methyldehydroalanine (Puddick et al., 2014).

78 Bloom-forming cyanobacteria can release MCs into aquatic reservoirs when the cells die due
79 to natural or man-made actions, causing water quality problems and sanitary hazards for aquatic
80 wildlife and public health due to their hepatotoxic and carcinogenetic potential (Rastogi et al.,
81 2014; Brooks et al., 2016; Tokodi et al., 2018). Humans are exposed to MCs through
82 contaminated drinking water ingestion, food chain or recreational contact. In recent years, many
83 studies have reported the bioaccumulation of MCs in freshwater and agricultural products
84 destined to consumption (Martins and Vasconcelos, 2014; Rastogi et al., 2014). Moreover,
85 MCs-contaminated water used for crop irrigation has an immense impact on plant growth and
86 development; and thus, cause a significant yield loss (Freitas et al., 2015b; Lee et al., 2017;
87 Machado et al., 2017b); in addition, MCs may have an influence on the development of
88 rhizospheric microbiota associated to agricultural crops (El Khalloufi et al., 2016; Cao et al.,
89 2017). MCs are chemically stable owing to their cyclic peptide structure. Conventional water

90 treatments such as coagulation, flocculation, sedimentation and filtration can only remove the
91 intact cells, whereas MCs persist in water when cyanobacterial cells are lysed (Keijola et al.
92 1988; Chorus and Bartram, 1999). Therefore, using microorganisms capable of degrading MCs
93 under environmental conditions has been increasingly studied worldwide as a low-cost and
94 high-efficient biological method to detoxify MCs-contaminated water bodies (Jones et al.,
95 1994; Manage et al., 2009). In this paper, we aim to review the ecological impact of application
96 of MCs-contaminated irrigation water on plant-soil ecosystem. Therefore, our purpose is to: (a)
97 highlight current findings over the last decade of fate and mode of action of MCs in vascular
98 terrestrial plants; (b) describe the impact of MCs on soil microbial community structure and
99 function; (c) provide the most current data of MCs fate in soil ecosystems and (d) emphasize
100 bioaccumulation of these cyanotoxins in edible parts of agricultural plants. Table 1.

101 **1. Mode of action and fate of MCs in plants and soil microorganisms**

102 MCs are the most widespread and studied cyclic heptapeptides produced during bloom events,
103 mainly by *Microcystis* genus and released into water bodies via cell rupture caused by both
104 natural senescence and abiotic stress (Dawson, 1998; Sivonen and Jones, 1999; Ross et al.,
105 2006). Dissolved MCs persist in water bodies for several days to weeks during natural
106 decomposition of cyanobacteria and after bloom decay and disappearance (Lahti et al., 1997;
107 Harada and Tsuji, 1998; Zastepa et al., 2014). Their total concentration in surface waters range
108 from less than 1 µg/L to 29,000 µg/L (Oudra et al., 2001; Spoof et al., 2003; Billam et al.,
109 2006; Nasri et al., 2008; Giannuzzi et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2011). Furthermore, cells of
110 *Microcystis aeruginosa* persist ashore in dry crusts for several months preserving the intact
111 MCs within. Once the crust is re-wet, MCs are rapidly released into the surrounding water
112 (Jones et al., 1995). It is also known that the half-life of MCs, introduced into soil by irrigation
113 via bloom-containing water, vary from 1 to 17.8 days depending on toxin variant, soil chemical
114 composition and bioactivity (Miller and Fallowfield, 2001; Chen et al., 2008; Edward et al.,

115 2008). Therefore, the use of these contaminated water for crop irrigation is reported by several
116 studies as having adverse effects on the growth and development of cultivated plants as well as
117 on soil microorganisms (Corbel et al., 2014a). In this section, all studies relative to the fate and
118 mode of action of MCs in vascular terrestrial plants and their associated microbiota will be
119 reviewed and critically analyzed. Table 2.

120 **2.1. Phytotoxic effects of MCs on plant growth and physiology**

121 Overall, MCs seem to have adverse effects on: (a) seed germination (Saqrane et al., 2008;
122 Chen et al., 2012b; El Khalloufi et al., 2012; Lahrouni et al., 2012; Corbel et al., 2015; Cao et
123 al., 2018a); (b) seedling growth and development (McElhiney et al., 2001; M-Hamvas et al.,
124 2003; Pereira et al., 2009; El Khalloufi et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2012b; El
125 Khalloufi et al., 2013; Lahrouni et al., 2013; Freitas et al., 2015a; Lahrouni et al., 2015; Liang
126 and Wang, 2015; Cao et al., 2018 b; Pham, 2018; Zhu et al., 2018); (c) nitrogen uptake
127 (Lahrouni et al., 2012, 2016) and (d) photosynthetic assimilation (El Khalloufi et al., 2011;
128 Lahrouni et al., 2012; Liang and Wang, 2015; B-Oliveira et al., 2016; Machado et al., 2017b),
129 besides inducing acute oxidative stress (El Khalloufi et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2011; Chen et
130 al., 2012a; Lahrouni et al., 2012 ; El Khalloufi et al., 2013; B-Oliveira et al., 2016; Pereira et
131 al., 2017; Cao et al., 2018 a, b). However, response of plants to MCs depends on the following:
132 (a) plant species; (b) toxin variant; (c) toxin concentration applied; (d) toxin nature (purified or
133 crude extract); (e) exposure time; (f) method of irrigation (surface or spray irrigation); and (j)
134 biochemical composition of agricultural soil in which the plant subject is studied (Abe et al.,
135 1996; McElhiney et al., 2001; Saqrane et al., 2008; Chen et al., 2013; Máthé et al., 2013; Cao
136 et al., 2018c). Photosynthetic assimilation is a vital physiological process enabling the plants to
137 biosynthesize their own organic matter. Also, chlorophyll plays a pivotal role in this process by
138 capturing light and transforming energy (Liang and Wang, 2015). MCs seem to decrease
139 chlorophyll content in vegetable cells; and thus, reduce the net photosynthetic capacity

140 (Pflugmacher et al., 2007b; Saqrane et al., 2009; Lahrouni et al., 2013; Liang and Wang, 2015).
 141 Therefore, the decrease of photosynthetic rate results in the growth inhibition of affected plants
 142 (Kummerová et al., 2006; Liang and Wang, 2015). Several studies conducted on MCs
 143 phytotoxicity have used cyanobacterial crude extract containing more than one MCs congener;
 144 thus, plants are affected by the combined bioactivities of the different MCs congeners.
 145 However, further studies on simultaneous uptake and synergetic phytotoxic effect of these
 146 congeners are required.

147 Table 1: Impact of MCs-LR on seeds germination, growth and development, and physiological functions
 148 of several agricultural species.

Plant species	MC analogue	[MC] µg/L	Effect	Reference
<i>Brassica napus</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	120-3,000	Seedlings growth ↓ Germination percentage ↓ Seedlings height ↓ Elongation of primary roots ↓ POD & SOD induction ↑ Cotyledons Chlorosis and/or Necrosis	Chen et al., 2004
<i>Brassica rapa</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	400-6,400	ROS generation ↑ SOD, APX, CAT induction ↑ Lipid peroxidation Loss of membrane integrity	Chen et al., 2012a
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	(MCs) ^{CE}	10	Yield of fruits ↓ Vitamin C content ↓ Fruit soluble sugar ↓ Fruit organic acid ↓	Zhu et al., 2018
		10-1,000	Protein content ↑ Root & shoot size ↓ Plant height ↓ Stem diameter ↓ Leaf area ↓ Root dry weight ↓ Leaves chlorosis & necrosis	
		100-1,000	Absence of fruits	
<i>Daucus carota</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	10-50	Root fresh weight ↓ Photosynthetic capacity ↑ Root mineral content (K, Mg, Mn, Cu, Zn) ↑ Ascorbic acid content ↓	Machado et al., 2017b
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	5.9-56.4	Root growth ↓	Pereira et al., 2009
	(LR) ^P	30-6,000	Seedlings growth ↓ Shoot fresh weight ↓ SOD activities of leaves ↑	Wang et al., 2011
	(LR) ^{CE}	20,000	Radicle length ↑	Corbel et al., 2015
	(LR) ^P	1-100	Root fresh weight ↑	Freitas et al., 2015
		100	Leaves fresh weight ↓	

	(LR/RR) ^{CE}	(0.5-10/ 0.15-3)	GST activity of roots ↑ GPx activity of roots & leaves ↓ Leaves mineral content ↓ GST activity ↓ CAT, POD, SOD activities ↑	B-Oliveira et al., 2016
	(LR) ^P	1,000	Photosynthetic capacity ↑ Germination rate ↓ CAT activity ↑	Cao et al., 2018a
<i>Lens esculenta</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	500-4,200 2,100-4,200 2,400	Fresh weight ↓ Chlorophyll a + b content ↓ Photosynthetic capacity ↓ Height ↓ Leaf number ↓	Saqrane et al., 2009
<i>Lepidium sativum</i>	(LR) ^{CE & P}	1-10 10	GST activity of roots ↑ GPx activity ↑ Leaf length ↓ Root length ↓ Fresh weight ↓	Gehring et al., 2003
<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	11,120-22,240	Seedlings growth ↓ POD activity ↑ Leaves necrosis	El Khalloufi et al., 2012
	(LR) ^{CE}	16,680-22,240 22,240 100-5,000 ≥20,000	Germination rate ↓ Photosynthetic capacity ↓ Radicle length ↓ Radicle development ↓	Corbel et al., 2015
<i>Malus pumila</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	300-3,000	POD activity ↑ SOD activity ↑	Chen et al., 2010
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	(LR) ^{CE/S}	5	Primary root development ↓ Sprouts development ↓ Lipid peroxidation ↑ SOD activity ↑	Pflugmacher et al., 2006
	(MCs) ^{CE}	2,220-22,240	Seedlings growth ↓	El Khalloufi et al., 2011
	(MCs) ^{CE}	11,120-22,240	Root length ↓ Nodules number ↓ Photosynthetic capacity ↓ Phenolic compounds content ↑ Protein content ↑	
	(MCs) ^{CE}	22,240 5-20 10-20 20	Seeds germination ↓ Chlorophyll content ↓ POD activity ↑ Shoot & root dry weight ↓ PPO activity ↑ CAT activity ↑	El Khalloufi et al., 2013
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	24-120 600-3,000	SOD ↑ Seedlings growth ↓ Primary root elongation ↓ Height ↓	Chen et al., 2004
	(LR) ^P	500-4,000	Shoot fresh & dry weight ↑ Root growth ↓ Crown root primordia ↓	Chen et al., 2012b
	(LR) ^{CE}	2,000-4,000 4,000 260-13,000	Crown root length ↓ Crown roots number ↓ GPx activity ↑	Azevedo et al., 2013

	(LR) ^{CE}	100-3,000	Root, stem & leaf dry weight ↓ height ↓	Liang and Wang., 2015
	(LR) ^{CE}	1,000-3,000	Leaves chlorophyll content ↓ Photosynthetic capacity ↓	
	(LR) ^P	5-50 50-500	Protein content ↓ Amylose content ↓ SOD activity ↑	Cao et al., 2018b
			Root length, surface area & volume Root weight ↓ Root weight ↓ CAT activity ↑ MDA activity ↑ Rice root exudation ↓ SOD activity ↓	
<i>Petroselinum crispum</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	500 100-1,000	Chlorophyll a + b content ↓ Carotenoids content ↓	Pereira et al., 2017
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	11,600	Germination rate ↓ Primary root length ↓ Lateral root number ↓ Epicotyl length ↓ Lateral root primordia genesis ↓	Saqrane et al., 2008
		1,000	Photosynthetic capacity ↓	Saqrane et al., 2009
<i>Sinapis alba</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	10,000-30,000	Primary root growth ↓ Lateral root formation ↓ Cotyledon growth ↓ Anthocyanin content ↓	M-Hamvas et al., 2003
	(LR) ^P	500-50,000	Fresh weight ↓ Cotyledon length ↓ Hypocotyl length ↓ Root length ↓ Chlorophyll content ↓ Cotyledon chlorosis POD activity ↑	M-Hamvas et al., 2010
<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	(LR) ^P	5-5,000 10-5,000 50-5,000	Fresh weight ↓ Shoot length ↓ Root number ↓ Chlorophyll content ↓ Leaf & shoot tissue necrosis	McElhiney et al., 2001
<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	(LR) ^{CE/S}	0.5	Leaf size & number ↓ Leaf chlorosis CAT, POD & SOD activities ↑ GST & GR activities ↑ α - & γ -tocopherol content ↑	Pflugmacher et al., 2007a
<i>Triticum durum</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	11,600	Primary root length ↓ Lateral root number ↓ Epicotyl length ↓	Saqrane et al., 2008
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	(LR) ^{CE/P} & (RR) ^P	0.5	Germination rate ↓ Primary root length ↓ Shoot length ↓ Chlorophyll a + b content ↓ Photosynthetic capacity ↓ Leaf & root GSH activity ↑ Leaf & root GPx ↑	Pflugmacher et al., 2007b
	(LR) ^{CE}	≤ 20,000	Germination rate ↓	Corbel et al., 2015

<i>Vicia faba</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	50-100	Germination rate ↓	Lahrouni et al., 2011
		100	Shoot & root nitrogen content ↓	
		50-100	Nodule dry weight ↓	Lahrouni et al., 2013
			Shoot dry weight ↓	
			Root length ↓	
			Root dry weight ↓	
			Nodule dry weight ↓	
			Nodule number ↓	
			Chlorophyll a + b content ↓	
			Photosynthetic capacity ↓	
	CAT & POD activities ↑			
	PPO activity ↑			
	Phenolic compounds content ↑			
	Shoot & root Na ⁺ content ↑			
	Shoot C ²⁺ & K ⁺ content ↓			
	Root necrosis			
	10,000	Cortical cell size ↓	Lahrouni et al., 2015	
	40,000	Root elongation ↓		
	10,000-80,000	Root hair formation ↓		
	100	Tissue lysis & root tip necrosis	Lahrouni et al., 2016	
		Shoot and dry weight ↓		
		Nodule number & dry weight ↓		
		Total nitrogen content ↓		
		GS & Fd-GOGAT activities ↓		
<i>Vigna angularis</i>	(MCs) ^{CE}	500	Fresh weight ↑	Pham, 2018
<i>Vigna cylindrical</i>		20-500	Radicle & shoot length ↓	
<i>Vigna radiata</i>		200-500	Fresh weight ↓	
		500	Germination rate ↓	
		20-500	Radicle & shoot length ↓	
		200-500	Germination rate ↓	
<i>Zea mays</i>	(LR) ^{CE}	11,600	Fresh weight ↓	Saqrane et al., 2008
		Primary root length ↓		
		Lateral root number ↓		
			Epicotyl length ↓	

149 ↑, increase in comparison to control group; ↓, decrease in comparison to control group; CE, crude extract; P,
150 purified toxin; S, spray irrigation. MCs: Total concentration of MCs in crude extract was applied with dominance
151 of MCs-LR.
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153 2.2. Phytotoxicity mechanisms of MCs in vegetable cells.

154 The phytotoxic mechanism of MCs is not fully understood to date. However, phytotoxicity
155 of MCs may refer in first place to the inhibition of phosphatases activity, generating deleterious
156 reactive oxygen species (ROS) and DNA damaging (MacKintosh et al., 1990; Garg and
157 Manchanda, 2009; Chen et al., 2011). To our knowledge, MCs bind irreversibly with
158 serine/threonine protein phosphatases 1 and 2A (PP, PP1 and PP2A) in eukaryotic cells of both
159 humans and vascular plants (Honkanen et al., 1990; Monks et al., 2007). PPs seem to be

160 involved in a number of physiological and molecular processes (Sheen, 1993; Takeda et al.,
161 1994; Pereira et al., 2011); thus, their inhibition in vegetable cells seems to affect many vital
162 functions, including: (a) Carbon dioxide fixation (Carter et al., 1990); (b) Sucrose biosynthesis
163 (Siegl et al., 1990); (c) Light inducible gene expression (Sheen, 1993); (d) Starch storage
164 (Takeda et al., 1994); (e) Chromosomes separation in metaphase; (f) Pollen tube growth (Smith
165 and Walker, 1996); (j) Carbon and nitrogen metabolism (Toroser and Huber, 2000); (h) Cell
166 elongation, hair root development and root branching by interfering with auxin translocation
167 (Garbers et al., 1996; Chen et al., 2013). Also, MCs interfere with the specific activity of
168 glutamine synthase (GS) and ferredoxin-glutamate synthase (fd-GOGAT); and thus, decrease
169 the nitrogen assimilation efficiency in both shoots and roots (Lahrouni et al., 2016).

170 In a study conducted by Chen et al. (2013), MCs remarkably decreased the transcription of
171 *CRL1*, *WOX11* and *OsNial* in rice root in a concentration-dependent manner; and thus, led to
172 root growth inhibition of rice seedlings. *CRL1* and *WOX11* genes are indispensable for rice
173 crown root organogenesis via an auxin-induced mechanism (Inukai et al., 2005; Zhao et al.,
174 2009). On the other hand, *OsNial* gene encodes nitrate reductase, an enzymatic source of
175 endogenous nitric oxide (NO), along with nitric oxide synthetase (Ali et al., 2007; Cao et al.,
176 2008). NO is essential for crown root primordia initiation in rice seedlings (Xiong et al., 2009).
177 In dicots, NO mediates the auxin response for lateral root initiation and root hair formation
178 (Pagnussat et al., 2002; Lombardo et al., 2006; Guo et al., 2008; Xuan et al., 2008; Guo et al.,
179 2009). Moreover, MCs inhibit polar translocation of auxin from shoot tips to rice roots; and
180 thus, significantly reduce root growth because of its vital role in stimulating root hair and lateral
181 root formation. (Overvoorde et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2013). Much of the deleterious effects of
182 MCs in plants is related with alterations in the metabolism of plants, as revealed by proteomics
183 (Azevedo et al., 2014; Freitas et al., 2015a).

184 Also, MCs seem to interfere with anthocyanins biosynthesis in plants tissues (M-Hamvas et
185 al., 2010). These photoprotective pigments reduce photoinhibition and photobleaching of
186 chlorophyll under light stress conditions (Steyn et al., 2002). Consequently, their decrease in
187 plants exposed to MCs may explain the decrease in photosystem II efficiency reported by
188 several studies (Sagrane et al., 2009; El Khalloufi et al., 2012; Lahrouni et al., 2013). Moreover,
189 MCs are the prime suspect as the cause of loss of plant membrane permeability, since the
190 mineral assimilation of plants exposed to MCs has been altered with decrease and increase in
191 the content of some minerals compared to control groups (Lahrouni et al., 2013; Freitas et al.,
192 2015b; Machado et al., 2017b). Minerals participate in several physiological functions
193 (including photosynthesis), considered vital to plants surviving; and thus, perturbation of
194 mineral assimilation may result in plant dysfunction and appearance of physiological and
195 histological disorders (Soetan et al., 2010). However, phytotoxicity mechanisms of MCs in
196 plants is still unclear and should be the subject of future research.

197 **2.3. Plant defense mechanisms against MCs-exposure**

198 The exposure of terrestrial plants to MCs induce the generation and accumulation of
199 reactive oxygen species (ROS), and thus activate the antioxidative defense through biosynthesis
200 of several antioxidant enzymes such as catalase (CAT), peroxidase (POD), superoxide
201 dismutase (SOD), polyphenol oxidase (PPO) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) (Chen et al.,
202 2004; Pflugmacher et al., 2006; Pflugmacher et al., 2007a; Chen et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2011;
203 Chen et al., 2012a; El Khalloufi et al., 2013; Lahrouni et al., 2013; Cao et al., 2018b); besides,
204 antioxidant molecules such as Ascorbic acid, tocopherols and phenolic compounds
205 (Pflugmacher et al., 2007a; El Khalloufi et al., 2011; Lahrouni et al., 2013; Machado et al.,
206 2017b). These biochemical plant constituents are crucial to neutralize and overcome the
207 deleterious effect of ROS. Furthermore, vegetable cells under toxin stress increase the

208 production of malondialdehyde (MDA) (Cao et al., 2018b). This chemical is a sensitive
209 indicator of lipid peroxidation and intracellular injury (Grundy and Storey, 1998)

210 On the other hand, vegetable cells can metabolize MCs molecules via a conjugation
211 reaction to reduced glutathione (GSH) catalyzed by glutathione S-transferase (GST)
212 (Pflugmacher et al., 1998). Therefore, biosynthesis of GST to detoxify MCs may help diverse
213 plants to survive under toxic stress (Gehring et al., 2003; Pflugmacher et al., 2007a, b; Freitas
214 et al., 2015a). Detoxication of MCs via an enzymatically formed glutathione conjugate is an
215 intrinsic defense mechanism. It is also suggested that plants under toxic stress may increase the
216 secretion of organic acids in root exudate to enhance the bioavailability of pollutants to
217 degrading microflora in rhizospheric soil (Joner et al., 2002; White and Kottler, 2002). In a
218 study carried out by Cao et al. (2018b), the two organic acids, tartaric acid and malic acid were
219 higher in rice root exudate in response to MCs-exposure.

220 In a study conducted by Machado et al. (2017b), Photosynthetic activity in carrot shoots
221 exposed to MCs-stress has increased which is contradictory to other studies carried out on other
222 plant species (Pflugmacher et al., 2007b; Saqrane et al., 2009; El Khalloufi et al., 2012;
223 Lahrouni et al., 2013; Corbel et al., 2015; Liang and Wang, 2015). According to this study, all
224 minerals recognized as crucial for photosynthesis (K, Mg, Fe, Cu, Zn) increased in plants
225 exposed to MCs, which results in the observed increase in photosynthetic rate. It can be
226 hypothesized that the increase of mineral content in response to toxic stress is a defense
227 mechanism to restore altered functions boosted by several minerals.

228 **2.4. Allelopathic effect of MCs on plant associated microbiota**

229 Studies on the allelopathic effect of MCs on soil microbial structure and function are still
230 scarce. However, in a study carried out by El Khalloufi et al. (2011), the use of MCs-
231 contaminated water for irrigation had hazardous impact on the development of symbiosis
232 between rhizobia strains and the leguminous plant *Medicago sativa*. The growth of rhizobial

233 strains was significantly decreased under MCs-exposure. In another study conducted by
234 [Lahrouni et al. \(2011\)](#), MCs had also a negative effect on the rhizobia-*Vicia faba* symbiosis in
235 which growth and development of rhizobial strains were significantly reduced.

236 Microbial indicators such as soil respiration, potential nitrification and enzyme activities
237 are often used to assess impact of pollutants on soil microbial community structure and function
238 ([Winding et al., 2005](#)). In an early study conducted by [Cao et al. \(2017\)](#), MCs-enriched
239 irrigation water can dramatically alter soil microbial functions. Therefore, biological activity of
240 soil microbiota has been assessed through enzymatic activities of dehydrogenase, urease,
241 phenol oxidase, β -glucosidase, acid phosphatase and alkaline phosphatase. However, only
242 dehydrogenase and phenol oxidase activities were affected under MCs-exposure, in which
243 dehydrogenase activity has increased while phenol oxidase activity has been highly inhibited.
244 Dehydrogenase activity is relevant to microbial respiration ([Bolton et al., 1985](#)), its increase
245 may refer to more carbon mineralized from some degrading bacteria ([Cao et al., 2017](#)). On the
246 other hand, MCs have caused a decline in soil potential nitrification rate as well, because active
247 nitrifying bacteria have decreased in abundance. Moreover, MCs have altered the ability of soil
248 microorganisms to use carbon sources ([Cao et al., 2017](#)). Gene abundance analysis of main soil
249 functional groups of microorganisms can also serve as a strong indicator of the impact of
250 pollutants on the microbial diversity ([Chen et al., 2015](#)). Through gene analysis in soil, [El](#)
251 [Khalloufi et al. \(2016\)](#) have reported the potent toxicity towards rhizosphere microbiota of
252 *Medicago sativa* in bulk soil, root-adhering soil and root tissue in response to MCs-exposure.
253 The toxicity has highly decreased the abundance of several bacterial genera including
254 *Actinobacteria*, *Gemmatimonas*, *Deltaproteobacteria* and *Gammaproteobacteria*.

255 The toxicity mechanism of MCs on soil bacteria is not fully investigated to date. Although,
256 [Dixon et al. \(2004\)](#) have shown that MCs could alter the permeability of cell membranes of a
257 culture of *Escherichia coli*. It was also proved that cyanobacteria can release antibacterial

258 substances into surrounding water to compete with other microbes (Oufdou et al., 1998;
259 Ostensvik et al., 1998). These substances are probably transported to soil via irrigation water
260 and responsible of altered soil microbial structure. We can also suggest that MCs inhibit
261 bacterial phosphatases activity in the same way as for animals and vascular plants. However,
262 Further studies are required to fully understand toxicity mechanism of MCs in prokaryotic cells
263 and their influence on microbial community structure and function in general.

264 **3. Fate of MCs in soil-plant ecosystem**

265 MCs may be introduced into soil-plant ecosystem via irrigation with cyanobacteria-
266 contaminated water. Consequently, the use of these MCs-enriched water for the irrigation of
267 food plant crops poses a great threat to human health and soil ecosystem (Corbel et al., 2014a;
268 Cao et al., 2017). Once MCs are present in the soil, they can be absorbed and translocated into
269 the edible organs of cultivated plants (Corbel et al., 2014a). More MCs are available to plants
270 owing to their persistence in the soil and infiltration into the ground water beneath (Eynard et
271 al., 2000; Corbel et al., 2014b). Furthermore, cyanobacteria cells added to soil via irrigation
272 take more time to break down and release the MCs within, which results in a long-term
273 persistence in soil (Chen et al., 2006). In this section, all studies relative to accumulations of
274 MCs in both soil and plant tissues are fully reviewed and investigated for critical analyze.

275 **3.1. Fate of MCs in soil: degradation and sorption behavior**

276 MCs are chemically stable under natural conditions owing to their cyclic heptapeptide
277 structure. They can withstand high temperature (Zhang et al., 2010), resist to chemical
278 hydrolysis at high and low pH values, 3 weeks at pH 1 and 10 weeks at pH 9 (Harada et al.,
279 1996) and resist to photolysis under natural sunlight (Tsuji et al., 1995). Thus, biodegradation
280 by microbial community seems to be a promising process to depollute soils from MCs (Chen
281 et al., 2006; Rastogi et al., 2014). However, biodegradation of MCs in soil ecosystems has been

282 rarely investigated, while the whole process has been extensively studied in freshwater
283 ecosystems. To our knowledge, soils with higher microbial activity accelerate the degradation
284 of MCs within 10 to 16 days (Miller and Fallowfield, 2001). Moreover, MCs degradation is
285 relatively faster in soils with high content of organic carbon, in which the half-life ranged from
286 9.9 to 17.8 days for MC-RR, 6.0 to 17.1 days for MC-LR and 7.1 to 10.2 days for MC-Dha. In
287 this study, high organic content seems to be propitious to the growth of degrading bacteria
288 (Chen et al., 2006). Cao et al. (2018c) have found that the addition of high concentrations of
289 sodium nitrate and humic acid had a stimulatory effect on biodegradation of MCs in soil, in
290 which the half-life ranged from 3.6 to 3.0 days with sodium nitrate and 1.7 days with humic
291 acid. In the same study, the use of glucose and ammonium chloride as fertilizer had an inhibitory
292 effect on biodegradation process. It seems that biodegradation is influenced by the type of
293 nitrogen and carbon sources. Even though, some bacteria can use MCs as the nitrogen sole
294 source (Valeria et al., 2006). In previous studies, MCs-degrading bacteria prefer glucose as
295 carbon sole source. When it is available in habitat, other carbon sources such as MCs are no
296 longer needed. Consequently, the addition of glucose in soil can slow biodegradation rate (Park
297 et al., 2001; Valeria et al., 2006).

298 MC molecules have a polar structure. They carry negative charges in the two carboxylic
299 acids functions and a positive charge in the arginine guanidino group at neutral pH (one arginine
300 in MC-LR and two arginine in MC-RR). Consequently, they persist in soil by adsorption onto
301 oppositely charged particles (Järvenpää et al., 2007). The sorption behavior of MCs in soil
302 depends on the soil type and the soil clay content. That is to say, high clay content would have
303 higher MCs adsorption. MCs can bind with the metal ions in clay due to the presence of nitrogen
304 and oxygen atoms in their chemical structure (Chen et al., 2006). However, MCs are weakly
305 sorbed onto clay particles at soil pH 5.6, in which both the components exhibit a negative charge
306 (De Maagd et al., 1999; Miller et al., 2001). In other studies, it was shown that the sorption

307 capacity of MCs was very low for silty and sandy soils, in which the amount of clay was very
308 poor (Chen et al., 2006; Corbel et al., 2014a). New data reveal that MCs persisted in soil after
309 harvest; and thus, have a continuous negative impact on the growth and development of crops
310 and their associated microflora (Lee et al., 2017). Once MCs are introduced to soil, the half-life
311 vary from 1 to 17.8 days depending on toxin variant and soil chemical composition (Chen et
312 al., 2008; Edwards et al., 2008). In general, the adsorption of MCs in soils is low, which results
313 in higher bioavailability to agricultural plants. That is to say, the low sorption of MCs to soil
314 particles increases their mobility and bioavailability to both plants and microorganisms
315 (Machado et al., 2017a). Also, the high affinity of MCs to soil particles expose the plant-soil
316 system to a long-term exposure. Otherwise, MCs are like any other mineral and organic ions
317 adsorbed on clay-humic complex. There is an exchange between MCs adsorbed on clay and
318 humic acid particles and free ones in soil solution (Chen et al., 2006; Thirumavalavan et al.,
319 2012). However, the sorption of MCs onto soil particles and its degradation by native flora
320 reduce its bioavailability to plants. Therefore, plants cultivated without soil in hydroponic
321 systems are more exposed to free MCs whose accumulation in plant organs is potentiated (Mc
322 Elhiney et al., 2001; Chen et al., 2004; Peuthert et al., 2007; Crush et al., 2008; Mohamed and
323 Al Shehri, 2009; Saqrane et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2010). The sorption behavior, toxin
324 availability and biodegradation process mainly depend on soil parameters (pH, organic carbon
325 content, etc.). However, data on MCs behavior in soil are scarce. Further studies are required
326 to fully understand the sorption/degradation of MCs considering all the physicochemical factors
327 of soil.

328 **3.2. Accumulation of MCs in food crops**

329 Once MCs are introduced into agricultural soil, they are able to accumulate in edible organs
330 of agricultural plants (Chen et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2011; G-Praena et al., 2014; R-Oliva et
331 al., 2014; B-Oliveira et al., 2016; Dorbac et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2017; Machado et al., 2017b;

332 [Cao et al., 2018d](#); [Zhu et al., 2018](#)), which results in the food chain contamination and human
333 health hazard ([Corbel et al., 2014a](#); [Machado et al., 2017a](#)). The tolerable daily intake of MCs
334 contained in edible plants was set in 0.04 µg per kilogram of body weight per day ([WHO, 2011](#)).
335 Nonetheless, several recent studies have shown that MCs concentration in some edible plants
336 exceed the recommended daily intake set by WHO ([Dorbac et al., 2017](#); [Lee et al., 2017](#); [Zhu
337 et al., 2018](#)). MCs contamination varies among vegetable species and cultivars, between plant
338 organs, between different developmental stages, and between irrigation methods ([Lee et al.,
339 2017](#); [Levizou et al., 2017](#)). It has been shown that roots accumulate higher amount of toxin
340 than leaves of the same species ([Peuthert et al., 2007](#); [Mohamed and Al Shehri, 2009](#); [Corbel
341 et al., 2016](#); [Levizou et al., 2017](#)). Cultivated plants such as radish and carrot have been found
342 to accumulate considerable amounts of MCs in the edible root system. However, roots of edible
343 plants are not consumed by humans in most cases ([Mohamed and Al Shehri, 2009](#); [Lee et al.,
344 2017](#)). Moreover, MCs accumulation seems to vary among different developmental stages. It
345 has been shown that lettuce seedlings at early cotyledon stage exhibited the highest MCs content
346 compared to respective tissues of 2 and 4 leaves stages ([Levizou et al., 2017](#)). Similarly, MCs
347 content in cucumber roots was higher at seedling stage, followed by flowering and fruiting
348 stages respectively ([Zhu et al., 2018](#)). It seems that plants accumulate considerable amounts of
349 toxin at early stages of development, but more studies are required to fully understand this
350 process. On the other hand, time-exposure to MCs seems to have an effect on toxin
351 accumulation rate in plant tissues. In the same previous study conducted by [Zhu et al. \(2018\)](#).
352 Treatment of cucumber plants with MCs at different stages (seedling, flowering and fruiting
353 stages) has resulted in the increase of MCs content in fruits in a time-dependent manner.

354 The mechanisms of MCs uptake from soil; besides, their translocation within the plant
355 tissues are still unexplored. However, it has been suggested that MCs are absorbed from soil by
356 root system via plant membrane transporters with affinity for peptides ([Peuthert et al., 2007](#);

357 [Crush et al., 2008](#); [Saqrane et al., 2009](#); [Tegeger and Rentsch, 2010](#)). Plants can also absorb
358 water through leaves and stems ([Hu et al., 2016](#)). Consequently, edible leaves and stems of
359 agricultural plants exposed to MCs via spray irrigation may raise more concern about the risk
360 of consuming such products than those irrigated via other methods. It has been also reported
361 that MCs were translocated to seeds of edible plants such as rice, pepper and lettuce which may
362 lead to their presence in new plants ([Chen et al., 2012b](#); [R-Oliva et al., 2014](#); [Levizou et al.,](#)
363 [2017](#)). Moreover, rice plants grow in flooded soils and absorb more water than other crops
364 which results in a long-term contact with MCs containing-water; and thus, a high accumulation
365 rate of MCs in shoots, stems and roots ([Cao et al., 2018b](#)). Yet, data about MCs accumulation
366 rate in plants cultivated in real field conditions are scarce. Although, MCs have been detected
367 in the rice grains of plants irrigated with natural bloom-containing water in Taihu Lake, China.
368 The toxin concentrations ranged from 0.04 to 3.19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ of dry weight ([Chen et al., 2012b](#)).
369 Also, MCs have been found in edible leaves and roots of six plants (radish root; and leaves of
370 lettuce, cabbage, dill, arugula and parsley) irrigated with MCs-containing well water in Asir
371 region, southwest of Saudi Arabia, in which, MCs content ranged from 0.05 to 1.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ of fresh
372 weight. In the same study, roots accumulate higher amounts of toxin than shoots. Except for
373 radish, the roots of the other plants are not consumed by human ([Mohamed et Al Shehri, 2009](#)).
374 In general, several agricultural plants have been reported to accumulate higher amounts of MCs
375 in non-edible roots and shoots, which may result in the contamination of chain food through
376 consuming meat and dairy products from domestic animals feeding on MCs-contaminated
377 shoots and roots.

378 Table 2. Bioaccumulation of MCs-LR in edible organs of several agricultural plants. Only toxin
379 accumulation in edible parts was considered.

Plant species	Dose applied ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$)	Exposure time (days)	Analyzed organ	Concentration found in plant organ (ng/g)	References
<i>Brassica napus</i>	24 ^{CE}	10	Aerial part	2.61 ^{FW}	Chen et al., 2004
	120 ^{CE}			8.32 ^{FW}	
	600 ^{CE}			123.57 ^{FW}	

	3,000 ^{CE}			651.00 ^{FW}	
<i>Capsicum annum</i>	17.82 ^{CE}	7	Fruits Seeds	1.03 ^{DW} 7.41 ^{DW}	R-Oliva et al., 2014
	245 ^{CE}	98	Fruits	118 MC-LR ^{DW} 77 dm-MC-LR ^{DW}	Dorbac et al., 2017
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	100 ^{TMC} 100 ^{TMC}	7	Fruits	15.43 ^{FW} 29.64 ^{FW}	Zhu et al., 2018
<i>Daucus carota</i>	10 ^{CE}	28	Root	≥ 200 ^{DW}	Lee et al., 2017
	50	28	Root	5.23 ^{FW}	Machado et al., 2017b
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	30 ^P 300 ^P 1,000 ^P 3,000 ^P 6,000 ^P	8	Shoots	69 ^{FW} 133 ^{FW} 520 ^{FW} 703 ^{FW} 1148 ^{FW}	Wang et al., 2011
	2 ^{CE} 5 ^{CE} 10 ^{CE}	15	Leaves	6.32 ^{FW} 10.14 ^{FW} 15 ^{FW}	B-Oliveira et al., 2016
	10 ^P	28	Leaves	> 60 ^{DW}	Lee et al., 2017
	2.62 ^{TMC} 5.22 ^{TMC} 122.4 ^{TMC}	60	Leaves	2.2 ^{FW} 19.3 ^{FW} 78 ^{FW}	Cao et al., 2018d
<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>	100 ^{CE}	7	green fruit mature fruit	4.41 ^{FW} 10.52 ^{FW}	G-Praena et al., 2014
	100 ^P	7	green fruit mature fruit	5.15 ^{FW} 10.83 ^{FW}	
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	2.62 ^{TMC} 5.22 ^{TMC}	60	Grains	0.7 ^{FW} 2.1 ^{FW}	Cao et al., 2018d

380 TMC, Total MCs concentration; CE, crude extract; P, purified toxin; FW, fresh weight; DW, dry weight.
381

382 4. Conclusion

383 MCs are the most relevant cyanotoxin released into eutrophic reservoirs during blooms
384 events worldwide. Their persistence and long half-life in irrigation water raise more concern
385 about their fate and mode of action in soil-plant complex. Over the last decade, several studies
386 have reported the phytotoxic effect of MCs on growth and physiology of agricultural plants.
387 MCs seem to be involved in growth inhibition of so many plants through interruption of
388 photosynthesis, mineral assimilation including nitrogen uptake; besides, generating deleterious
389 ROS involved in disruption of other physiological functions as well. On the other hand, plants
390 can mitigate the phytotoxic effect of MCs through biosynthesis of antioxidative molecules
391 enabling the vegetable cell to neutralize and wipe out ROS; in addition to, detoxifying MCs
392 through a GSH-conjugate mechanism. Moreover, MCs seem to have an inhibitory effect on

393 rhizospheric microflora associated to agricultural plants which may result in their lack in soil;
394 and thus, the reduction of plant growth. However, more data are still needed to investigate and
395 fill the gaps in knowledge about MCs-phytotoxic pathways in both vegetable cells and soil
396 bacteria; besides, their overall impact on microbiota function and structure in soil. Also, data
397 are still scarce about bioavailability of MCs and their adsorption onto soil particles. So far, MCs
398 seem to have high sorption affinity to clay particles which results in a long-term persistence.
399 However, soils rich in organic matter are propitious for MCs-degrading bacteria which results
400 in a short half-time of MCs in soil. Also, soils with less clay content and low pH results in high
401 bioavailability of MCs to plants and microorganisms. Although, chemical composition of soil
402 seems to affect both sorption and bioavailability of MCs in soil. More research is required to
403 better understand the underlying chemical and biological processes involved. Furthermore,
404 MCs are able to translocate from soil to roots, and then to shoot system which alters the quality
405 of plant food products and raises more concern about the risk of consuming such products. To
406 date, MCs translocation from soil to roots and within the plant system are still unexplored.

407 **Conflict of interest**

408 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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